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LITIGATION AND PERSONAL INCOME TAX REVENUE GENERATION IN RIVERS STATE.

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Abstract: This study examined the impact of litigation on personal income tax revenue generation in Rivers State using evidence from the Internal Revenue Service of Rivers State. The study aimed to determine the relationship between tax litigation measures and personal income tax revenue in Rivers State. The sample for this study was 57 staff of the Rivers State Internal Revenue Services, with adequate knowledge of the variables under study. Data were collected from respondents (staff) using questionnaire instruments that were found to be reliable with Cronbach's alpha. Descriptive statistics, such as frequency and percentages, were used to facilitate the conversion of raw data into meaningful form that was easy to understand and interpret in relation to the study variables. The mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions 1 and 2. The hypotheses were tested to explain the relationship between the dependent and independent variables using the Pearson product moment correlation coefficient at the 0.05 alpha level of significance. This study established that: There is a positive and strong significant relationship between litigation and personal income tax revenue (such as personal income and capital gains) in Rivers State. The study concludes and recommends that enforcement measures, especially the use of litigation, are key in the realization of personal income tax revenue. Hence more administrative and enforcement measures should be in place for the Internal Revenue Service of Rivers State to boost revenue generation.

Keywords: Litigation, Personal Income, Tax, Revenue, Enforcement, Revenue Generation.

Introduction

Revenue refers to income generated by a government, organization, or individual from various sources, such as taxes, sales, services, or investments. In Rivers State, revenue generation has taken a dwindling decline due to the inability of government, organizations, individuals, and other agencies to pay taxes and increase the state's revenue base. The associated problems with revenue decline as observed include: tax evasion; illegal avoidance of tax payments, and non-compliance to tax laws, thereby reducing government revenue generation. Bala et al. (2021) posits, that there are tax avoidance situations in which the government may take serious actions to

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minimize tax liability, which is potentially depriving the government of revenue. Their argument implies that revenue leakages may involve unintended losses due to inefficiencies, corruption, and poor tax administration. However, this study aims to ascertain the veracity of using litigation as an enforcement mechanism to increase revenue generation in the state. Similarly, Ayodeji (2014) and Agbeni et al. (2011) agreed that political instability, unstable governments, conflicts, and policy changes affect revenue generation and allocation, whereas global economic factors, such as trade wars, exchange rate fluctuations, and global economic trends, impact revenue. The extent to which these challenges impact revenue requires further investigation to examine whether litigation can increase state government revenue through effective tax policies, efficient revenue administration, and robust financial management strategies to ensure a stable and sustainable revenue stream.

Taxation is believed to play a crucial role in the economic life of a developing country, such as Nigeria. Today, the Internal Revenue Service in Rivers State is in need of an effective and efficient tax system to generate enough revenue to finance economic activities and improve growth and development. However, the realization of economic growth through tax revenue has become a mirage. According to Bala et al. (2021), employing litigation as a tax enforcement measure is likely to increase revenue using legal proceedings, such as lawsuits and court actions, to enforce tax laws and collect taxes owed by individuals or entities. These assumptions and positions are the major trust of this research in determining the extent to which litigation can have a positive impact on increasing tax revenue in Rivers State.

Statement of the problem

Low tax compliance is a serious concern in many developing countries. This is because it limits the government's capacity to raise revenue for developmental purposes (Torgler, 2013). In Nigeria, the tax administration is confronted with complex and thoughtful multidimensional problems. Ola (2007) and Kamin (2022) maintained that revenue collected from income tax of individuals and corporate bodies tend to be too low because of inadequate knowledge (tax literacy) and; poor association between tax authorities and taxpayers. However, whether their arguments are true is a subject for further empirical investigation. Second, Agbeni et al. (2011), Ayodeji (2014), and Kysar (2020) agreed that the insufficient number of quality and competent accountants among tax authorities' staff, untrained and unqualified tax personnel, and lack of skills on how to use information or other technical procedures on how to utilize information available for the assessment and calculating tax in a best suitable manner reduces tax revenue. While we may agree with their assumptions, there is a need to investigate empirically to determine whether training or technology affects tax revenue in Rivers State. Finally, litigation as a tax enforcement measure is observed to lead to increased revenue generation. However, the extent to which it positively or negatively impacts the payment of personal income tax revenue in Rivers State has not been ascertained. Therefore, this study intends to determine the impact of litigation on personal income tax revenue in Rivers State to identify litigation challenges and how it can help improve tax revenue generation.

Objectives of the study

This study primarily aimed to determine the relationship between tax litigation measures and personal income tax revenue in Rivers State.

The specific objectives are as follows:

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1. Determine the extent to which litigation impacts personal income tax revenue generation in Rivers State.
2. Examine the relationship between litigation and search and seizure on personal income tax revenue in the state of Rivers.

Research Questions

1. To what extent does litigation impact personal income tax revenue in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does the relationship between litigation and search and seizure affect personal income tax revenue generation in Rivers State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were developed and tested at the 0.05 alpha level of significance.

H₀₁ No significant impact of litigation on personal income tax revenue generation is observed in Rivers State.

H₀₂ No significant relationship exists between litigation and search and seizure on personal income tax revenue generation in Rivers State.

Significance of the Study

This study would be of tremendous benefit to the government, tax administrators, authorities, and scholars/researchers. This study would be of great benefit to the government of Rivers State and Nigeria, especially in this period of dwindling economy and low revenue generation. The shortfall in oil revenue, agricultural revenue, technological agencies, and others have affected the ability of the government to conduct its obligations to the citizenry. Therefore, this study will aid the government in understanding the factors that affect tax compliance and the effect of tax litigation on personal income tax revenue generation. Similarly, the suggestions made by this study on how to improve the existing tax enforcement strategies of the Nigerian tax system, at all levels of government vis-à-vis federal, state, and local levels, will increase tax revenue generation to a large extent. Thus, it would have tremendous effect on the revenue base of the government. Accordingly, the study provided an avenue through which tax administrators, controllers, inspectors, and relevant tax authorities can ascertain the effect of tax enforcement strategies on tax revenue in Rivers State, giving an insight into how tax payers react to tax enforcement procedures carried out by the relevant tax authorities. Finally; the study will add to the existing literature on tax enforcement strategies, such as litigations on tax revenue, to help future researchers interested in the subject matter and as a basis for further reference.

Scope of the study

The research study concentrated on tax enforcement measures applicable to personal income tax revenue in Rivers State, such as litigation and search and seizure with the objective of determining the impact of litigation on personal income tax revenue. The study was conducted on 57 tax authority officials of the tax unit/division in the Internal Revenue Service of the Rivers State. The population and sample size of 57 staff were drawn on the targeted population, and the study was conducted within the territory of Rivers State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A Conceptual Review of Litigation

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Tax litigation is a key issue in enhancing tax compliance. As a branch of enforcement, litigation involves compelling taxpayers to adhere to or obey the provisions of the relevant tax laws. It is directed at taxpayers who fall short of their tax responsibilities, and the measures include levies, searches and seizures, fines, and court actions (Miguel & Lopez-Rodriguez, 2014). According to them, litigation is defined as the act of making sure that people obey a particular law or rule or the process of settling disputes in court through a legal action or proceeding such as law suit to enforce compliance.

Mohammed (2015) looks at litigation as an effort in law that involves the application of all relevant laws that will assist tax officials in performing their duties. Although he agrees that these laws may not necessarily be related to only taxation, they are relevant to the enforcement of tax laws. The various enforcement measures under the Nigerian Tax Act include litigation, exercise of search and seizure, exercise of power to lay distress, denial of tax clearance certificate, imposition of penalty and interest, authority to the Attorney-General of the federation (AGF) to deduct unremitted withholding tax from funds due to relevant agencies of government and authority to the Nigeria Customs Services (NCS) to refuse clearance to any defaulting shipping company (Profundale, 2005).

Litigation is critical in raising revenue when court orders and rulings are upheld. While Bank (2015) sees litigation as the process of convincing tax payers to do the right thing, Bala et al. (2021) seek litigation as the use of appeals, pleading, and trial to drive home compliance by defaulters of the law. Notably, the justification for legitimizing enforcement will be eroded if it is wrongly and harshly applied. Bank (2015) maintains that tax authorities catch tax defaulters and cheats and increase the level of compliance by enforcing relevant tax laws, while KPMG (2016) observed that the aggressive tax enforcement procedures adopted by tax authorities in Nigeria to enhance compliance to recover unpaid taxes from defaulting tax payers are as inappropriate when compared with the approaches used worldwide. Hence, enforcement is the driving force that promotes tax compliance, and the inevitability of tax enforcement engenders self-assessment that can positively impact the revenue drive of the tax authorities and the state.

Tax monitoring, litigation, and enforcement

The application of tax monitoring, litigation, and enforcement as administrative mechanisms to achieve tax revenue targets is beneficial but, must be applied with caution due to its adverse consequences (Laggins 2022). The essence of taxation, as observed, is to benefit the citizens and not for punitive measures against the citizens because tax enforcement involves persuasions, force, and cohesion on tax payers to extract outstanding tax liabilities owed to the government. Litigation measures are applied to tax defaulters to correct behavior, improve tax compliance, and close the tax revenue gap (James & Alloy, 2004). They contend that there is no doubt in the existence of tax administration sanctions. However, the extent to which they are needed and the enthusiasm for enforcement raised questions and doubts.

Musa (2014) and Higgins (2022) noted that there are certain procedures employed by the relevant tax authorities, in accordance with the provisions of the laws and regulations, which include writing a demand notice on the taxpayers, to file their annual returns, allowing for objection to the assessment, if any amendment of the assessment, where necessary, appeals, then, collection and administration of those tax so collected. Procedures for the enforcement of delinquent taxes when voluntary compliance proves difficult are also laid

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down, which include but are not limited to the following: penalties, civil and criminal litigation, distraint and sale of defaulting taxpayer's property, search and seizure, use of tax clearance certificate, etc. Those procedures will not bar the tax authorities from taking advantage of the other procedures if it becomes necessary and expedient through litigation. However, rights of the tax payer are sought to be observed and protected when applying any of the procedures of enforcement. Is-haq (2010), aligning with Musa (2014), maintained that despite the well-arranged procedure for the enforcement of income tax in Nigeria and the enabling tax laws and regulations to that effect, non-compliance and defiance of payment of delinquent taxes by the defaulting tax payers persist, hence litigations.

Tax Litigation Problems and Enforcement Measures

Reviewing the works of Togler (2013), it appears that there is an overdependence on a single source of revenue generation. Over-reliance on a single revenue stream makes revenue generation vulnerable to fluctuations, while inefficient tax systems result in complex, outdated, or unfair tax laws, leading to reduced compliance and revenue. Agbeni et al. (2011) have also argued that corruption, such as bribery, embezzlement, and other corrupt practices for diverting revenue from intended purposes, indicates economic downturns, such as recession, inflation, and market fluctuations. Their proxies are clear indicators of sharp practices that are likely to reduce revenue. Reduced revenue from taxes and other sources can hinder the growth of the state's economy, while inadequate financial management, poor budgeting, forecasting, and financial planning lead to revenue shortfalls (Ayodeji, 2014). Some factors are responsible for the epileptic enforcement of tax defaulters that occasioned substantial revenue leakages to the government. These problems include but are not limited to the following:

Insignificant sums as fines: This problem is generally consistent with all tax laws or even legislation. Section 47 of the principal Act, for instance, provides a paltry sum of five thousand (₦5,000.) and five hundred (₦500) naira only as a fine for failure to avail the tax authorities of the relevant information needed for personal income tax assessment. Although, these have been increased to (₦500.00) and (₦50,000) naira only, respectively, by the personal income tax amendment Act of 2011, the persistent inflationary atmosphere in the country will render these fines totally insignificant and, therefore, unable to serve the purpose for which they were prescribed. Accordingly, taxable persons do not feel threatened by the existence of these sanctions and prefer to save their resources by evading tax for an insignificant fine or no risk at all.

Corruption by Tax Officials: High levels of corruption, manifested by extortions, bribery, compromise, and expropriation of tax revenue, are prevalent among tax officials (Matthias & Marie, 2014). This is occasioned by the lack of effective monitoring mechanisms, the lack of tax officials' motivation, and the general apathy of "tax administrators." The reason is near neglect by the government since personal income tax is notoriously barren in terms of revenue. Sadly, however, the government incurs huge revenue loss as a result of the corrupt attitude of tax officials. It is imperative to note that when revenue collectors become major actors in the depletion of state revenue, the state becomes helpless. Therefore, some States have devised means of significantly curbing or reducing the incidence of corruption among their revenue personnel through litigation.

Lack of Prosecution of Errant Taxable Persons: Despite the various terms of imprisonment and fines prescribed by the enforcement provisions, errant taxable persons or tax officers are rarely prosecuted, even in

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the face of pervasive tax evasion aided by tax personnel. Several reasons have been attributed to this want of prosecution, ranging from corruption to the slow judicial system and the infrequent sitting of the Tax Appeal Commissioners (TAC). The cost of prosecution is also a burden for tax authorities. These account for the decisions of the tax authorities to sometimes compound the offences on the payment by a taxpayer of part of the tax due, under section 48 FIRS (Establishment) Act (CTPA, 2004).

Political interference: Tax authorities in Rivers and Nigeria are all government parastatals. The Federal Inland Revenue Services (FIRS) the State Board of Internal Revenue (SBIR), and the State Internal Revenue Services (SIRS) are not self-accounting and efficient. They relied on their supervisory ministries' budget for logistics at all costs. Consequently, all emergency expenditure required for tax collection must be channeled to the supervising ministry if it was not initially budgeted for. With the provisions of section (1) of the FIRS Act, the long-awaited autonomy has been granted to the FIRS to grant it corporate status to defend its budget at the national assembly (CTPA, 2004).

Lack of motivation: The principal reason for persistent corruption is the lack of motivation of tax officers. "Tax officers (especially the field workers) suffer double jeopardy, in that they are hated by taxpayers and neglected by their masters (Government)." At the expense of repetition, it is common knowledge that most tax officers are bereft of modern facilities, while the workers are poorly remunerated (CTPA, 2004). Therefore, training and welfare are needed.

Tracking Tax Defaulters: The major challenge faced by tax authorities in their bid to enforce tax revenue is tracking tax defaulters. Tax defaulters employ all manner of antics to evade taxes. For instance, certain taxpayers operating in hotels, private schools, shopping malls, or other businesses in Rivers State now conceal their signposts and operate in a clandestine manner to avoid being tracked down by relevant tax authorities. Companies chargeable to the payment of Company's Income Tax (CIT), Education Tax (ET), and Value Added Tax (VAT) often change address at will without recourse to the tax authorities. In the same vein, many individual taxpayers maintain more than one place of residence, thereby creating the problem of tracking taxpayers down (CTPA, 2004). These tendencies point to the state's dwindling low revenue and poor economic base.

Inadequacy of Tax Defaulters' prosecution: Tax defaulters walk the street freely partly due to the perception of the public that tax defaulters are hardly viewed as having committed any serious offense. It seems that tax enforcement officers themselves have the same perception of tax defaulters and are not willing to prosecute them; rather, they prefer to use negotiation or other means of tax liability settlement (CTPA, 2004).

Litigation and Personal Income Tax Revenue

Litigation is a personal action that is instituted to compel payment or other purely civil actions. It is a proceeding in a court of competent jurisdiction by one party against another for the forceful compliance or protection of a private right or for the redress or prevention of a private wrong. The civil action may involve a private party suing another private party or a private party suing or being sued by the government, but the proceedings do not involve criminal proceedings. For example, under the Federal Inland Revenue Act, civil actions are provided for under Section 34(1), which states the following: "Without prejudice to any other provision of this Act, or any other law listed in the first schedule to this Act, any amount due by way of tax shall

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constitute a debt due to the service and may be recovered by a civil action brought by the service." Civil litigation presupposes that the FIRS has legally engaged the defaulting taxpayer with all the statutory demand notices, reminders, and distraint. Therefore, civil litigation is undertaken as a last resort to redress a particular civil wrong perpetrated against the Service. A criminal proceeding is defined as an action or proceeding put in place or prosecuted by the state in its own name against a person(s) who is accused of an offense. A criminal proceeding is ordinarily one that may result in the imposition of a sentence such as death, imprisonment, fine, or forfeiture of property if carried to an end. It is significant to acknowledge that the gamut of legal rules that guide the investigation, prosecution, adjudication, and punishment of crime as well as the protection of the constitutional rights of the accused constitute a criminal procedure. Under the Federal Inland Revenue Act, offences and penalties are listed under Part VI of the Act.

Again, under civil litigation, the FIRS strives to enforce its civil right against a particular tax direct assessment(s) who defied all the statutory assessments and demand notices issued by the service and duly served on them. The process culminating to a civil action instituted by the Service is as follows: The L&P Department of FIRS as claimant files a specially endorsed writ of summons and statement of claim at the Federal High Court in the location where the defendant(s) resides or carries on business. The writ of summons is accompanied by the claimant's witness statement on oath, which itself is supported by certified true copies of all public documents used in the course of correspondence (e.g., assessments, demand notices, and reminders) from the FIRS to the tax direct assessment. The suit is also supported by the written address of the claimant. The claimant witnesses must be officers of the service who are competent and conversant with the facts of that case as per their involvement in the process of tax administration with the officers/agents of the defendant(s). The claimant's witnesses must also be conversant with the documents attached to the witness statements on oaths and the court-relief documents. The claimant's court processes are then served on the defendant(s) who either by themselves or by a legal practitioner of their choice files a Memorandum of Appearance and a Statement of Defense along with the defendant(s) witness statements on oath, supported by necessary documents in their defense.

Accordingly, there is also a defendant's written address in reply to the law and fact issues raised in the claimant's written address. The defendant's Memorandum of Appearance, statement of defense, witness's statements on oath, and written address are then served on the claimant through the Legal and Prosecution Department (L&P). After a careful perusal of the defense, the solicitors may decide to file an amended statement of claim or further address or reply as the case may be. At a fixed named date for hearing of the case, the claimant applies to the court that pleadings have been exchanged and calls on its witnesses to adopt their statements and exhibits on oath in cause of examination-in-chief. At the end of the examination-in-chief, the counsel for the defendant(s) cross-examines each claimant's witnesses and, where necessary, re-examines them by the claimant's counsel. At the conclusion of the claimant's case, the defendant(s) starts its defense by calling on its witnesses to adopt its defense witness's statements/exhibits on oath. At the end of each defense's testimony, the witness will be cross-examined by the claimant's counsel and, where necessary, re-examined by the defendant's counsel. At the end of the case for the defense, counsel for the defense and claimant are

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respectively called upon to adopt their written addresses in support of their arguments and thereafter the court takes a date for Judgment.

Personal Income Tax and Capital Gains

Personal income tax for salaried employment in Nigeria is based on a Direct Assessment system. It is applicable under the provisions of the Personal Income Tax Act (PITA) Cap. P.8 LFN, 2004. The current deterrent measures for non-adherence include penalties of up to 25 000 naira (N25, 000) only for employers who fail to register their employees and remit such taxes to relevant authorities. Employers are also liable for the payment of all tax arrears. Employers failing to keep proper records would also face a penalty of only five thousand (N5,000) naira. These revenues generated would become the state's capital gain in revenue generation. Adekanola (1997) agrees that the meager fine tends to encourage tax evasion because the penalty for being caught is lower than the cost for noncompliance. The bulk of PIT is paid by employees, whose salaries are deducted at source and when meagre fines, evasion, and tax avoidance occur, there is a likelihood of reduced revenue generation, and the enforcement measure would be through litigation. The Chartered Institute of Taxation of Nigeria (CITN), (2002) identified some problems confronting PIT administration in Nigeria. They observed that tax administration in Nigeria is particularly difficult because the literacy level is low and record keeping is not yet a popular culture. According to them, there are insufficient tax officials to cover the field, maintaining that most of the officials are not adequately trained, ill-equipped, and corrupt. Governments in Nigeria are perceived as corrupt and selfish, to whom money (PIT) should not be voluntarily given. They observed that taxes paid most often end up in private pockets, not in public utilities. The foregoing not only makes compliance difficult but also makes it forceful and problematic.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework on which this study is based is the ability to pay theory developed by Kendrick (1939). It is the most popular and commonly accepted principle of equity or justice in taxation, and the assumption is that a country's citizens should pay taxes to the government in accordance with their ability to pay. The theory appears very reasonable and affirmed that taxes should be levied on the basis of an individual's taxable capacity. For instance, if the taxable capacity of a person A is greater than that of person B, the former should be asked to pay more taxes than the latter. This further suggests that if taxes are levied on this principle, justice can be achieved. However, our difficulties do not end here. When we put this theory into practice, our difficulties begin. Trouble arises with the definition of the ability to pay. Scholars of law and economists are not unanimous as to what should be the exact measure of a person's ability to pay. The main viewpoints to be advanced in this context of this theory are as follows:

Ownership of Property: Some economists believe that ownership of the Property is a superb basis for measuring an individual's ability to pay. This idea is out rightly Rejected on the ground that if a person earns a large income but does not spend on buying any property, he will then escape taxation. On the other hand, another person earning a small income buys properties and is subjected to huge taxation. Therefore, these suggestions appear absurd and unjustifiable.

Tax on the Basis of Expenditure: This theory also asserts that the ability or faculty to pay tax should depend on the expenditure that a person incurs. Meaning that the greater the

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expenditure, the higher the tax, and *vice versa*. This viewpoint appears unsound and unfair in every respect. For instance, a person with a large family to support has to spend more than a person with a small family. If we use expenditure as a yardstick to test one's ability to pay, the former person who is already burdened with many dependents will have to pay more taxes than the latter who has a small family. This is unjustifiable.

Income as the Basics: This theory also assumes that income should be the basis of measuring a man's ability to pay. It appears very just and fair that if a person's income is greater than that of another, the former should be asked to pay more toward the government's support than the latter. The assumption of income as the basis is popularly accepted because of the face value, and that is why in the modern tax system of the countries of the world, income has been accepted by individuals as the best test for measuring the ability to pay. Therefore, it becomes the theoretical framework used in this study to determine personal income tax revenue.

Empirical Review

Bala et al. (2021) assessed the effects of personal income tax on revenue generation. To assess the problem, two specific objectives were set to examine the effects of tax avoidance and evasion on revenue generation in Gombe State and the absence of information technology on revenue generation in Gombe. Tax avoidance and evasion have significant effect on revenue generation in Gombe State. The findings are in collaboration with Maryam's (2011) findings that tax avoidance and evasion are serious problems that affect revenue generation. This implies that tax avoidance and evasion were found to be a serious threat affecting personal income tax revenue generation in the state. A large number of tax payers avoid and evade paying their personal income tax by either lowering the amount of income owed or declining to report their actual income to the officials responsible for tax collection in the state. However, the population, methodology, or inferential statistics adopted for the study were not stated.

Kobe et al. (2018) investigated the relationship between good governance and compliance with personal income tax. The results of both the robust multiple and simple linear regression analyses show that there is a positive and statistically significant relationship between good governance and personal income tax compliance. Transparency and public accountability will engender an effective tax system. The current fight against corruption in Nigeria, the system of whistleblowing, and due process in government activities all point to good governance and are capable of delivering an efficient tax system and, by implication, high levels of tax compliance. This study, though, did not state the scope and population as well as the design of the study.

Agbeni et al. (2010) examined the relationship between culture and personal income tax evasion in Nigeria. It represents culture with legal enforcement, trust in the government, and religiosity. A hundred and five responses were analyzed using the chi-square statistics, percentages, and OLS method of regression to estimate the relationship between tax evasion and the independent variables. The study finds evidence of a strong positive and significant (at 10% level) association between tax evasion and legal enforcement. It also finds that a positive relationship exist between weak and arbitrary enforcement of tax laws and tax evasion. Finally, a positive and significant (at the 5% level) association was observed between trust in the government and tax evasion.

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The research design adopted in this study is a correlational research design. This design is a type of research methodology used to examine the relationship between two or more variables. This study focuses on determining whether and to what extent changes in one variable are associated with changes in another variable. The population of this study was the staff of Rivers State Internal Revenue Service (RIRS) Port Harcourt with sixty-six (66) staff as respondents. A valid sample size of 57 was obtained using the following Taro Yamene Formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

Where:

N = total population (600)

1 = is a constant

e = significance level (0.05)

The instrument for data collection adopted in this study was a structured questionnaire. The distribution and collection of the questionnaires were administered to the staff categorized into senior and junior in the tax unit/division of the Rivers State Internal Revenue Service. This was done in two ways: through proxy and personal collection and analysis. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 was used to analyze the obtained data. The null hypotheses were tested using Pearson’s product moment correlation statistics at the 0.05 level of significance. The decision to accept an item was that if the mean score was equal to or greater than 2.50, then the item was accepted as agreed but rejected as disagreed if the mean score was less than 2.50. The mean score was computed as follows: $\frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = 2.50$

ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

Univariate Analysis

Relationship between litigation and personal income tax revenue in the Rivers State

Table 1: Summary of descriptive statistics on the mean rating of litigation and personal income tax revenue in Rivers State.

S/N	Litigation N=57	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	The Rivers State Internal Revenue Service enforces tax revenue in Rivers State.	2.88	1.10	Agreed
2.	The Internal Revenue Service has an enforcement measures unit.	3.07	1.02	Agreed
3.	Active litigation unit in the Rivers State Internal Revenue Service.	2.84	1.00	Agreed
4.	The Internal Revenue Service (IRS) encourages the litigation approach as a means of increasing tax revenue in Rivers State.	2.79	1.19	Agreed
5.	The litigation unit of the enforcement measures do take the tax payers up to increase tax revenue in Rivers State.	2.96	1.15	Agreed
	Grand Mean	2.91	1.09	Agreed

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Source: Field Research Data, 2024

Table 1 shows that the summary of descriptive statistics on the mean rating of litigation and personal income tax revenue in Rivers State was 2.91, SD = 1.09. The respondents strongly indicated that the Internal Revenue Service has an enforcement measures unit (M = 3.07, SD = 1.02). This was followed by the fact that the litigation unit of the enforcement measures do take the taxpayers and defaulters up to increase tax revenue in Rivers State (M = 2.96, SD = 1.15). Next, the Rivers State Internal Revenue Service carried out enforcement measures on tax revenue in Rivers State (M = 2.88; SD = 1.10). Also, the litigation unit in the Rivers State Internal Revenue Service was active (M = 2.84; SD = 1.00). The least was on The Internal Revenue Service encouraging litigation approach as a means of increasing tax revenue in Rivers State. (M=2.79 SD=1.19). Based on the responses from the respondents, it was concluded that litigation had a strong effect on personal income tax revenue generation in Rivers State, which was 2.91, SD=1.19, among others.

Bivariate Analysis

H₀₁: No significant relationship exists between litigation and personal income tax in Rivers State.

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) on the relationship between litigation and personal income tax revenue in Rivers State, New Jersey.

Correlations

Variables		Litigation	Personal Income Tax (PIT)
Litigation	Pearson Correlation	1	.828**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	57	57
Personal Income Tax (PIT)	Pearson Correlation	.828**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	57	57

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Research Correlation Analysis, 2024.

Table 2 summarizes the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) on the relationship between litigation and personal income tax revenue in Rivers State. This shows that the pre-litigation has a positive and strong relationship with personal income tax revenue in Rivers State (r=.828). A p-value of .000 indicates a significant relationship between litigation and personal income tax in Rivers State (r=.828, p<.05). The null hypothesis one was rejected at the 0.05 level.

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

The results in Table 2 summarize the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) on the relationship between litigation and personal income tax revenue in Rivers State. This study revealed that litigation has a positive and strong relationship with personal income tax revenue in Rivers State (r=.828). The p-value of .000 indicates a significant relationship between litigation and personal income tax revenue in Rivers State (r=.828, p<.05). The

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null hypothesis one was rejected at the 0.05 level. The present result is in agreement with the findings of Ladle (2017), who evaluated the effect of statutory enforcement measures and revenue generation in Nigeria's federal and state tax authorities. The following variables were used: tax litigation, power of search and seizure, power of distraint for statutory enforcement and direct assessment, and company income tax for revenue generation. The researcher adopted descriptive statistics to analyze his findings. It was concluded that a positive relationship exists between statutory enforcement measures and revenue generation in both the state and federal government.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that revenue generation is critical for development and that tax enforcement measures (litigation and search and seizure) explored are sound predictors of tax revenue in Rivers State. This was because litigation, search, and seizure are all relative and have positive and significant effect on the personal income tax revenue in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher recommends the following;

1. There should be constant tax enforcement measures, especially litigation and search and seizures, that will assist in detecting fraudulent, incorrect and or underreporting of taxable incomes. The fear of regular litigation and search and seizure attempts by the State Internal Revenue will instill fear on tax defaulters.
2. Orientations, administrative policies, and stringent enforcement measures by the State Government will drive taxable income and generate revenue for the State.

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